

STUDIES IN ORGANO-ARSENIC COMPOUNDS. PART VII. SYNTHESIS OF ARSINDOLE DERIVATIVES.

BY HIRENDRA NATH DAS-GUPTA.

The present communication deals with the various attempts to prepare arsindole derivatives from ω -bromostyrene. The principal aim was to prepare a primary arsine like β -phenylvinyl-dichloroarsine which would produce arsindole derivatives by the application of the Friedel-Crafts' reaction (*cf.* Burrows and Turner, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, 119, 430).

The suitable intermediate compound for the preparation of β -phenylvinyl-dichloroarsine from ω -bromostyrene is either the arsonic acid, or a mercury derivative of the type $[(\text{Ph CH}=\text{CH})_2\text{Hg}]$. The yield of the arsonic acid from the styrene by Meyer's reaction (*Ber.*, 1883, 16, 1440) is very poor, due probably to the remarkable stability of the ω -bromostyrene in alkaline solution and its tendency to produce phenylacetylene and ethoxyphenylethane in alcoholic caustic alkali. Attempts at converting the sodium salt of the arsenic acid to the corresponding dihalide proved futile as it readily undergoes decomposition in acid medium giving arsenious acid. This behaviour is found to be analogous to that of benzyl-arsonic acid with hydrochloric acid.

The mercury derivative of styrene has been prepared by the two well known methods, *viz.*, (i) sodium amalgam method and (ii) by reacting the bromide with metallic sodium and mercuric chloride. The yield by the former process is very poor, whilst the latter method gives a better yield of mercury distyrene and a small quantity of styrene-mercuric bromide. Mercury distyrene when treated with arsenic trichloride yielded not the dihalogen derivative but mercuric chloride and non-arsenated derivative.

Burrows and Turner (*loc. cit.*) have been able to isolate $\text{Ph}(\text{Me})\text{AsI}$ by simply allowing phenyl-dichloroarsine in alcohol to react with methyl iodide and sodium hydroxide. The reaction product after acidification with hydrochloric acid and saturation with sulphur dioxide gave the arsine.

ω -Bromostyrene when treated with alcoholic phenyl-dichloroarsine in presence of alkali (*cf.* Burrows and Turner, *loc. cit.*) gave a small yield of the impure bromoarsine, which during purification by distillation under reduced pressure gave a yellow viscous mass identified to be 1-phenylarsindole.

All attempts in the above directions having proved unsuccessful attention was directed towards the preparation of different arsines from ω -bromostyrene by the adoption of the methods applicable to aromatic halides.

(i) ω -Bromostyrene was subjected to Fittig's reaction and a tertiary arsine was obtained along with small quantities of both primary and secondary arsines. The tertiary arsine on treatment with excess of arsenic trichloride at a high temperature (*cf.* Michaelis and Rees, *Ber.*, 1882, 15, 2876) gave 1-chloroarsindole through the intermediate unstable compound, $\text{PhCH}=\text{CHAsCl}_2$.

(ii) β -Phenylvinylidimethylarsine ($\text{PhCH}=\text{CHAsMe}_2$) was prepared from ω -bromostyrene and cacodyl bromide. The arsine was treated with chlorine to get the quinquivalent compound which was decomposed by heat. In this case also the reaction product was not a compound of the type $\text{PhCH}=\text{CHAs}(\text{Cl})\text{Me}$ but the ring-closure took place with the formation of 1-methylarsindole thus:—

(iii) The Grignard reaction is also available for the preparation of tertiary arsines, but by this method both the primary and secondary arsines are formed in appreciable quantities along with other by-products

The Grignard reagent from ω -bromostyrene was treated with cacodyl bromide and as expected, a poor yield of β -phenylvinyl dimethylarsine was obtained along with styrolene, 1:4-diphenylbutadiene, etc. In a similar way phenylmethyliodoarsine was allowed to react with the magnesium compound from ω -bromostyrene but in this case no reaction took place, the arsine distilled over unchanged and 1:4-diphenylbutadiene could only be isolated.

EXPERIMENTAL.

β -Phenylvinylarsonic Acid.—A solution of ω -bromostyrene (12 g.) in alcohol was added to an alcoholic solution of sodium arsenite (30 g. of arsenious acid in 40 g. of sodium hydroxide) and after standing for 24 hours the whole was heated under reflux with constant stirring for 48 hours. The oily layer was extracted with ether and the turbid aqueous layer was diluted with alcohol and allowed to stand overnight. The crystalline solid separating was filtered off, dissolved in water and reprecipitated by alcohol as needle-shaped crystals, yield of the sodium salt being 3.5 g. (Found: As, 26.9. $C_8H_7O_3AsNa_2$ requires As, 27.5 per cent). The alkaline mother liquor was neutralised with glacial acetic acid, filtered from the precipitated solids and the filtrate treated with a saturated solution of barium chloride and kept overnight. The precipitated barium salt (1 g.) crystallised from hot water. The free acid was isolated by treating the aqueous alcoholic solution of the sodium salt with the theoretical quantity of dilute hydrochloric acid and by fractional crystallisation.

Mercury Distyrene $[(Ph CH = CH)_2Hg]$.—(i) A mixture of ω -bromostyrene (18 g.), mercuric chloride (28 g.), sodium (5 g.) and dry benzene (60 c.c.) was kept overnight at room temperature. It was then heated under reflux on a water-bath for 8 hours and extracted several times with chloroform and the combined extracts precipitated with ether. The yellow precipitate was crystallised from chloroform, m.p. 150° . It is soluble in chloroform, acetone, sparingly soluble in benzene. It is not acted on by dilute alkali even on boiling. (Found: Hg, 49.3, 49.18. $C_{16}H_{14}Hg$ requires Hg, 49.2 per cent).

(ii) A mixture of ω -bromostyrene (10 g.), sodium amalgam (7.5%, 40 g.) and dry xylene (30 c.c.) and ethyl acetate, distilled over phosphorus pentoxide (5 c.c.), was heated under reflux for 7 hours at 140° . The reaction product was separated from the metallic mercury and the solvent evaporated off and the unchanged styrene was removed at $120^\circ/3$ mm. The residue was washed with excess of ether and finally extracted with chloroform. From

the chloroform extract the mercury derivative was isolated as above, m.p. and mixed m.p. 150°. (Found: Hg, 49.09. $C_{16}H_{14}Hg$ requires Hg, 49.2 per cent).

Styrolene-mercuric Bromide.—The solid left after extraction with chloroform in the above process was washed with excess of alcohol and then with water and the residue was dried in *vacuo*. It is insoluble in the common organic solvents and gives a black precipitate with pyridine. It does not melt up to 330°. (Found: Hg, 51.9. C_8H_7BrHg requires Hg, 52.2 per cent).

Fittig's Reaction with ω -Bromostyrene.

tris- β -Phenylvinylarsine [(Ph CH = CH)₃ As].—Sodium (10.5 g.) in the form of wire was taken in a round-bottomed flask provided with an upright condenser and a dropping funnel and allowed to remain for 1 hour in dry benzene (100 c.c.) containing 3 c.c. of ethyl acetate. A mixture of ω -bromostyrene (42 g.) and arsenious chloride (18 g.) was introduced into it. In about 20 minutes the reaction became vigorous and the reaction was controlled by alternately immersing the flask in ice-cold water and water at ordinary temperature and finally it was heated on a water-bath for 1 hour more and allowed to stand for 12 hours. The resulting brown viscous mass was repeatedly extracted with benzene and the solvent evaporated off under reduced pressure. The excess of styrene was distilled at 89-90°/3 mm. The product in the distilling flask solidified to a hard mass on cooling which was dissolved in hot benzene and the solution on concentration gave crystals of arsine, which were recrystallised from methyl alcohol in needle-shaped crystals, m.p. 82°. It is extremely soluble in benzene, toluene, carbon disulphide; soluble in ether, carbon tetrachloride, nitrobenzene, ethyl acetate and is soluble in hot acetic acid, methyl and ethyl alcohol; picrate, m.p. 100°. (Found: C, 74.6; H, 5.2; As, 19.2. $C_{24}H_{21}As$ requires C, 75.0; H, 5.4; As, 19.5 per cent).

β -Phenylvinyl dimethylarsine, [Ph CH = CH·AsMe₂] was prepared in a similar way as the previous compound starting from ω -bromostyrene (36 g.), sodium (9.2 g.), cacodyl bromide (86 g.), dry benzene (200 c.c.) and ethyl acetate (3 c.c.). The reaction was not so vigorous as the previous one and no cooling was necessary and the reaction was completed by heating the mixture for 5 hours on a water-bath. The reaction product was extracted with ether, solvent evaporated off and the viscous oil was distilled at 125-35°/5 mm. It is a yellow oil possessing an

offensive odour. (Found : C, 57.1 ; H, 5.9 ; As, 35.9. $C_{10}H_{13}As$ requires C, 57.6 ; H, 6.2 ; As, 36.05 per cent).

Grignard Reaction with ω -Bromostyrene.— ω -Bromostyrene (9 g.) reacted with magnesium (1.2 g.) in dry ether (100 c.c.) in presence of methyl iodide and a crystal of iodine. The last trace of magnesium was dissolved by heating the whole for 1 hour on a water-bath. Cacodyl bromide (9 g.) in ether (20 c.c.) was added drop by drop. After the addition was complete the reaction product was heated on a water-bath for 3 hours. After decomposition by cold dilute hydrochloric acid, the ethereal layer was removed and the aqueous layer extracted several times with ether. On evaporation of the solvent an oil was obtained which on fractionation gave (i) up to $65^{\circ}/5\text{mm.}$, mainly cacodyl bromide, (ii) and an oil at $125\text{--}140^{\circ}/5\text{ mm.}$ The solid residue in the flask on crystallisation from alcohol gave shining plates (arsenic-free), m.p. 135° . The second fraction was redistilled at $125\text{--}35^{\circ}/5\text{ mm.}$ (Found : As, 35.7. $C_{10}H_{13}As$ requires As, 36.05 per cent).

β -Phenylvinyltrimethylarsonium Iodide, $[\text{PhCH} = \text{CHAsMe}_3\text{I}]$, prepared by heating β -phenylvinyl dimethylarsine with excess of methyl iodide, separated as a yellow solid. It was washed with ether and dissolved in chloroform. The chloroform extract was concentrated and poured into ice-cold ether when needles were obtained, m.p. 155° . It is very soluble in methyl alcohol, chloroform, sparingly in carbon disulphide and insoluble in benzene, ether and petroleum ether. (Found : As, 21.1. $C_{11}H_{16}IA_s$ requires As, 21.4 per cent).

Mercuric Chloride Double Salt $[\text{PhCH} = \text{CHAsMe}_2, \text{HgCl}_2]$.—Ethereal solutions of mercuric chloride and β -phenylvinyl dimethylarsine in molecular proportions were mixed together and the precipitated solid was dissolved in chloroform and reprecipitated by ether, the operation being repeated several times. Finally it was crystallised from chloroform, m.p. 131° . (Found : Hg, 41.5. $C_{10}H_{13}As\text{Hg}$ requires Hg, 41.7 per cent).

tris- β -Phenylvinylmethylquaternary Arsonium Iodide, $(\text{PhCH} = \text{CH})_3\text{AsMeI}$ was crystallised from alcohol as needles, m.p. 95° . (Found : As, 14.2. $C_{23}H_{24}IAs$ requires As, 14.2 per cent).

Synthesis of Arisindole Derivatives.

1-Chloroarsindole.—tris- β -Phenylvinylarsine (10 g.) and arsenic trichloride (35 c.c.) were heated for 7 hours at 180° . The reaction product was treated with excess of 20% hydrochloric acid and the oil obtained was

dissolved in excess of ether, the ethereal solution washed with dilute hydrochloric acid, and dried over calcium chloride. The ether was evaporated off in an atmosphere of carbon dioxide and the oil distilled at $120-35^{\circ}/5\text{mm.}$ as a light yellow oil with a very irritating odour. [Found : As, 35.3; M.W. (cryoscopic in benzene), 216.3. $\text{C}_9\text{H}_9\text{ClAs}$ requires As, 35.2 per cent. M.W., 212.5].

It was identified as 1-chloroarsindole by its methyl derivative (*cf.* Das-Gupta, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 15, 354) and mercuric chloride double salt of the methyl derivative, m.p. and mixed m.p. 151° .

1-Methylarsindole.—A solution of β -phenylvinyl dimethylarsine in dry carbon tetrachloride was saturated with dry chlorine. The solvent was removed under reduced pressure and the remaining mass was gradually heated to $185-90^{\circ}$. Decomposition took place with evolution of methyl chloride, volatile chloroarsines, etc. The product was washed with dilute hydrochloric acid and then extracted with ether, the solvent removed and the oil distilled at $138-48^{\circ}/5\text{mm.}$ This was redistilled at $140-45^{\circ}/5\text{mm.}$ as a golden yellow oil. The mercuric chloride addition product melted at 151° . [Found : As, 39.1; M.W. (cryoscopic in benzene), 190.5. $\text{C}_9\text{H}_9\text{As}$ requires As, 39.06 per cent. M.W., 192].

1-Phenylarsindole.—A mixture of phenylarsenious chloride (9 g.) and ω -bromostyrene was allowed to stand for 24 hours with caustic soda solution (10 g. in 20 c.c. of water) at room temperature. It was then heated for 10 hours. The mixture was filtered through glass wool and the unaltered oil separated and the aqueous layer acidified with excess of hydrochloric acid in presence of alcohol. The solution was then saturated with sulphur dioxide, when a brown oil separated which was distilled at $165-76^{\circ}/3\text{mm.}$ as a brown oil. It was redistilled at $165-70^{\circ}/3\text{mm.}$ [Found : As, 29.6; M.W. (cryoscopic), 251. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{11}\text{As}$ requires As, 29.5 per cent. M.W., 254].

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DEPARTMENT OF APPLIED CHEMISTRY,
UNIVERSITY COLLEGE OF SCIENCE
AND TECHNOLOGY, CALCUTTA.

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